

Liquid-phase assisted spark-plasma sintering of SiC nanoceramics and their nanocomposites with carbon nanotubes

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Abstract

The appropriate conditions for liquid-phase assisted spark-plasma sintering (SPS) were identified for the fabrication of both SiC nanoceramics and their nanocomposites with carbon nanotubes (CNTs). A parametric study of the nanoceramics and nanocomposites with a given type of CNTs showed that the SPS temperature (as measured by the radial optical pyrometer) optimizing their densification, nanograin size, and mechanical properties is 1700 °C (soaking for a few minutes), below which there is incomplete densification, and above which there is obvious grain growth with no benefit in hardness or toughness in the case of the nanoceramics, and prejudicial to both properties in the case of the nanocomposites due to the CNT degradation. It was also shown that the nanocomposites have smaller nanograins than their nanoceramic counterparts, and are softer but tougher. Extension to nanocomposites with different types of CNTs confirmed these trends, and showed that the CNT features do not condition the densification, microstructure or mechanical properties of these nanocomposites.

Keywords: SiC; CNTs; spark plasma sintering; nanoceramics and nanocomposites; colloidal processing.

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1. Introduction

Nanostructured ceramics, also referred to simply as nanoceramics, are often harder and stronger than their conventional counterparts with larger grain sizes, and are therefore in principle more appealing for use as engineering ceramics in those applications requiring resistance to contact damage and wear [1]. To name explicitly just a few, this includes for example armour components for the protection of both personnel and vehicles, as well as a large variety of tribocomponents (seals, gears, bearings, valves, etc.). Nanoceramics also offer other unusual properties, such as superplasticity, optical transparency, etc., so that they are attractive as novel ceramics both structurally and functionally [2]. With these expectations in mind, a great amount of effort is being devoted to nanostructuring ceramics. Unfortunately, an undesirable effect of nanostructuring is generally the accompanying loss of toughness [1,3,4]. Brittleness is the main handicap of ceramics in general, and it is aggravated in the case of nanoceramics which can limit their otherwise extensive potential in certain structural applications. This has motivated a flurry of research activity on toughening nanoceramics, and one attractive way to do it is by reinforcing them with carbon nanotubes (CNTs) [5-9]. Thus, both nanoceramics and ceramic/CNT nanocomposites are currently research fields with ample popularity within the ceramics community.

Liquid-phase-sintered SiC is one of those widely-used engineering ceramics whose nanostructuring could be particularly important for structural applications, as has been demonstrated recently [10-14]. The interest in SiC is because it is much harder and stiffer than other common advanced ceramics (i.e., Al₂O₃, ZrO₂, Si₃N₄, etc.), and liquid-phase sintering toughens it (due to residual stresses promoting weak interfaces and therefore intergranular fracture, so that the toughness increase is more marked with grain coarsening/lengthening) and,

most importantly, enables its densification under smoother conditions (i.e., lower temperature with shorter soaking time) and therefore at lower fabrication costs. Even more worthwhile is nanostructuring the corresponding composites with CNTs, since these nanocomposites are tougher and more wear resistant than the nanoceramic counterpart [15]. Both materials could be fabricated today by spark plasma sintering (SPS), one of the most solidly established ultrafast sintering techniques, and whose industrial implementation has grown considerably over the last few years. This provided strong motivation for the present study, which was aimed at identifying the optimized SPS conditions for these nanoceramics and nanocomposites.

2. Experimental procedure

The ceramics and composites that were the focus of the present study were fabricated from custom home-made powder mixtures of nano-SiC+nano-YAG (weight ratio 9:1) without and with 7 vol.% (i.e., 4.6 wt.%) of seven different types of CNTs (i.e., with different morphology and/or surface functionalization). The starting materials were all available commercially (Nanostructured and Amorphous Materials Inc., USA), and were used in their as-received condition. Note that SiC is commonly densified using YAG liquid phase, which can be obtained directly from YAG particles as done here or by combining Y_2O_3 and Al_2O_3 particles in a 3:5 molar ratio. The content of YAG used is sufficient to achieve full densification of SiC via both liquid-phase assisted SPS [15] and conventional pressureless liquid-phase sintering [16], whereas 7 vol.% of CNTs falls within the normal concentration added as reinforcing phase [9].

The mixtures were first dispersed at pH ~10 in a mixture 9:1 by volume of de-ionized water and ethanol to a total solids loading of 5 vol.% with the aid of commercially-available polyelectrolytes (ProduktKV5088, Zschimmer-Schwarz, Germany; DuramaxTM D-3005, Rohm

& Haas, USA; Hypermer KD-7, Croda, USA), then sonicated, and lastly freeze-dried (Cryodos, Telstar, Spain) at -50 °C and 0.3 MPa for 24 h. More details on the powder features and on the aqueous colloidal processing can be found elsewhere [17,18]. The so-obtained powder mixtures were subsequently densified by SPS (Dr. Sinter SPS-2050, Sumitomo Coal Mining Co., Japan). Briefly, the powder mixtures were all loaded individually into graphite dies (12 mm inner diameter) lined with graphite foil and surrounded by a graphite blanket (1 cm thick), and were heated to the desired target temperature under uniaxial pressure in a dynamic vacuum atmosphere. The heating ramp was set at 200 °C·min⁻¹ up to 600 °C, and at 100 °C·min⁻¹ thenceforth. The pressure was increasingly applied during the first 2 min of heating, and maintained thereafter. A parametric SPS study was implemented involving target temperatures in the range 1600–1800 °C (as measured by an optical pyrometer focused radially on the interior of a 2.5 mm depth hole machined in the central region of the die), uniaxial pressures in the range 60–100 MPa, and dwell times in the interval 0–5 min. Note that the SPS temperatures being reported here are then applicable for SPS furnaces equipped with radial optical pyrometer, and should be handled with caution if other setups are used. After the completion of the SPS cycle, the load was released and the electrical power was shut off to allow rapid cooling (i.e., in 1–2 min) to room temperature. The shrinkage curves logged experimentally with the dilatometer of the SPS furnace were then corrected for the expansion of the graphite parts to obtain the real shrinkage curves of the powder mixtures themselves, and next converted to densification curves.

The SPSed ceramics and composites were broken, and their fracture surfaces were observed under field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM; Quanta 3D FEG, FEI, The Netherlands). Besides identifying the fracture mode, grain sizes were also estimated from several of these FE-SEM images taken randomly. Selected materials were also characterized by

X-ray diffractometry (XRD; D8 Advance, Bruker AXS, Germany), but only to **infer** whether the secondary intergranular phase was amorphous or crystalline. The composites with CNTs were also characterized by Raman spectroscopy (Nicolet Almega XR, Thermo Scientific, UK) to assess the CNT state.

The SPSed ceramics and composites were also polished to a 1- μm finish using routine ceramographic methods to evaluate their hardness **and to estimate their** fracture toughness by Vickers indentation tests (MV-1, Matsuzawa, Japan) [19] at 98 N load (ten separate indentations on each material). **Specifically, the hardness was calculated using the expression $H = 2P/d^2$ and the toughness using $K_{IC} = 0.016(E/H)^{0.5} P/c^{1.5}$, where P is the load, E the elastic modulus, d the length of the diagonal of the residual impression, and c the semi-length of the surface trace of the radial cracks.**

3. Results and discussion

Figs. 1A–B show the densification curves measured for various SPS target temperatures in the range 1600–1800 °C under 75 MPa pressure and 5-min soaking time for the ceramics and composites with ref-CNTs (0.5–2 μm length, 10–20 nm thickness, and OH^- surface functionalization), respectively. Below 600 °C, the temperature at which the optical pyrometer already controls the SPS cycle, what occurs is the elimination of the organic compounds used during the aqueous colloidal processing to deflocculate the concentrated suspensions. By way of example, Fig. 2 shows a typical evolution of the vacuum level as a function of the SPS temperature up to 600 °C, where one can see the broad peak of pressure loss between 80 °C and 450 °C (centred at ~ 150 °C) attributable to the volatilization of the organic deflocculants. In Figs. 1A–B, it can be seen that all the densification curves have the same shape. In particular,

there is first a linear stretch of very moderate densification attributable to the powder compaction. There is next a sudden jump in densification at 1120–1200 °C, followed by a stretch of greater densification up to the target temperature. And lastly, there is a final stretch of isothermal densification up to a certain limiting value. This latter is not necessarily 100%, as seen in the density–temperature SPS curves of Fig. 1 and more clearly in the exemplifying density–time SPS curve of Fig. 3 for the case without CNTs with target temperature of 1600 °C.

The abrupt densification observed at 1120–1200 °C in all SPS curves is attributable to the formation of a low-viscosity liquid because the ternary system Y_2O_3 – Al_2O_3 – SiO_2 has a eutectic point at ~1345 °C [20], and it is well known that the actual SPS temperatures can become hundreds of degrees higher than those measured by the radial pyrometer focused on the graphite die. The FE-SEM observations on compacts whose SPS cycle was interrupted at temperatures just below and just above 1200 °C, such as the ones presented by way of example in Fig. 4 for the case of the composite with ref-CNTs interrupted at 1094 °C and 1255 °C, support this explanation by showing less-particulate YAG.

Figs. 5A–C and 6A–C show representative FE-SEM images of the fracture surface of the ceramics and composites with ref-CNTs fabricated by SPS at 1600 °C, 1700 °C, and 1800 °C, respectively, under 75 MPa pressure and 5-min soaking time. It can be seen that there are always equiaxed SiC nanograins, and, in the case of the composites, also CNTs dispersed within the nanograin matrix. The XRD patterns, such as the one shown in Fig. 7 by way of example for the nanoceramic fabricated at 1700 °C, did not show YAG peaks, thus indicating that the intergranular secondary phase is essentially amorphous. This is not unusual in this type of material [14,21], and is attributable to the ultrafast cooling used in SPS together with the SiO_2 impurities in the SiC nanopowder shifting the composition of the secondary phase to the

difficult-to-crystallize zone in the ternary $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{--Y}_2\text{O}_3\text{--SiO}_2$ system [22]. It can also be seen in Figs. 5 and 6 that the nanograin size increases with increasing SPS temperature, as expected. Also, intergranular fracture is observed for both the nanoceramics and the nanocomposites, which is also as expected for this type of material with weak interfaces [23-26].

Table I lists the densification degrees achieved in these nanoceramics and nanocomposites for the different SPS condition used. Clearly, the materials fabricated at 1600 °C are still porous, whereas those fabricated at 1650 °C are near fully-dense if soaked at this temperature sufficiently (i.e., 3 min or more). This latter seems to be a requirement because a 5-min soaking at 1600 °C is more beneficial in terms of densification than simply reaching 1650 °C without soaking. At 1700 °C and above, both the nanoceramics and the nanocomposites are already fully dense if soaked for a few minutes. This temperature of 1700 °C, applied only for 5 min, is ~400 °C lower than the 2100 °C required for $\beta\text{-SiC}$ nanopowders to reach 98% of theoretical density by solid-state SPS (i.e., without sintering additives) at a similar pressure of 70 MPa for 30 min [27], these latter conditions in addition resulting in coarse-grained ceramics, which puts the advantages of the liquid-phase assisted SPS into perspective.

Table II lists the values of average grain size, hardness, and fracture toughness of the nanoceramics and nanocomposites at the different target SPS temperatures. It can be seen that the nanograin size increases with increasing SPS temperature, and that, under identical SPS conditions, the nanocomposites have smaller nanograins than the nanoceramics. This simply reflects that the CNTs, and other reinforcements, located at grain boundaries inhibit nanograin growth because they hinder the stages of solution, diffusion, and reprecipitation during liquid-phase sintering [15,28,29]. It can also be seen in Table II that hardness increases with increasing SPS temperature up to 1700 °C, at which it is maximum. Thus, hardness in the SPS temperature

range 1600–1700 °C correlates directly with the densification degree, increasing as the porosity decreases. The values of the nanoceramic hardness change little for SPS temperatures above 1700 °C, and if indeed they do correspond to any real slight reduction (which is hard to say due to the dispersion in both the hardness and the grain size values), this would be attributable to nanograin growth in accordance with the Hall-Petch relationship [30]. The nanocomposite hardnesses do appear to decrease for SPS temperatures above 1700 °C. Since these nanocomposites are fully dense and the nanograin size has little effect on the hardness as deduced from the nanoceramics, the most likely explanation is that the CNTs degraded above 1700 °C. This issue will be confirmed later anyway by Raman spectroscopy. One also observes in Table II that, for a given SPS temperature, the nanoceramic is comparatively harder than the nanocomposite, mostly attributable to the greater hardness of SiC.

As for the fracture toughness, it can be observed in Table II that in both cases this varies little or not at all with the SPS temperature. This simply reflects that the moderate nanograin growth contributes only marginally, if at all, to crack deflection at the weak interfaces. Note that the apparently greater toughness of the nanoceramic for SPS temperatures below 1700 °C is merely an experimental artefact attributable to the residual porosity (i.e., under Vickers indentation, part of the mechanical energy is consumed in densifying the material rather than in propagating the cracks). It can also be seen in Table II that the nanocomposites have greater toughness than their nanoceramic counterparts (i.e., 33-39% increase according to the Vickers indentation tests), which is mostly attributable to the CNTs hindering crack propagation and acting as "ligaments" between the SiC nanograins [8]. A recent comparative wear study has confirmed the toughening effect imposed by the CNTs [15], but it is nonetheless acknowledged

that detailed toughness measurements with methods other than Vickers indentation are still pending and needed.

Therefore, considering the microstructure and mechanical properties, 1700 °C emerges as the optimal SPS temperature (as measured by the radial optical pyrometer) in the case of the nanoceramics. This is extendable to the case of nanocomposites as long as it is confirmed that ref-CNTs survive the SPS at 1700 °C. In this context, Fig. 8 shows the Raman spectra of the as-received ref-CNTs and of the nanocomposites with ref-CNTs fabricated by SPS at temperatures in the range 1600–1800 °C. The nanocomposites exhibit a low-intensity band at $\sim 802\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ascribable to β -SiC, which is consistent with the XRD analyses ruling out the occurrence of $\beta \rightarrow \alpha$ polytype transformation during SPS. In the range $1000\text{--}3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ there are three bands attributable to the CNTs [31]: the D band at $\sim 1360\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (originating from the loss of translational symmetry of the hexagonal lattice due to structural disorder), the G band at $\sim 1595\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (first-order, fundamental lattice vibration corresponding to the C–C tangential stretching modes) and the 2D band at $\sim 2717\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (second-order overtone of the D band). Table III lists the intensity ratios I_D/I_G and I_{2D}/I_D , which are conventionally used to assess the CNT crystallinity (or structural quality). Ideally, I_D/I_G and I_{2D}/I_D should take the values 0 and 1, respectively. It can be seen that I_D/I_G decreases and I_{2D}/I_D increases to approach their ideal values with increasing SPS temperature up to 1700 °C, above which temperature the two trends reverse (i.e., I_D/I_G increases and I_{2D}/I_D decreases). Therefore, Raman spectroscopy confirms 1700 °C as being the optimal SPS temperature (as measured by the radial optical pyrometer) in the case of the nanocomposites too.

Consequently, with the information extracted from the study of the nanocomposites with ref-CNTs, nanocomposites with other types of CNTs were also prepared by SPS at 1700 °C (as

measured by the radial optical pyrometer) for 5 min under 75 MPa pressure. Figs. 9A–F show representative FE-SEM images of the fracture surface of these nanocomposites, and Table IV lists their relevant microstructural and mechanical features. Essentially, no distinction can be made among the different nanocomposites. Firstly, they all exhibit the same type of microstructure and mode of intergranular fracture. Secondly, they are all fully dense (i.e., ~99% densification or more), indicating that the exact type of CNTs does not condition the nanocomposite densification by SPS as long as the SiC nanoparticles forming the matrix, the YAG nanoparticles used as liquid-phase-sintering additive, and the CNTs introduced as reinforcements have been adequately dispersed (for example as done here by aqueous colloidal processing). Thirdly, the nanograin size is, within the large value of its dispersion, very similar in all cases, well below 100 nm and less than the nanograin size in their nanoceramic counterparts, as was justified above. And fourthly, regardless of the CNT features, the values of hardness and toughness (as measured by Vickers indentation tests) are fundamentally the same too (i.e., ~20 GPa and ~3 MPa·m^{0.5}, respectively), so that the nanocomposites are all softer and tougher than their corresponding nanoceramics, as also was justified above. Having said this, fine-CNTs are however a more advisable choice for the fabrication of these nanocomposites, in part because the balance of microstructural and mechanical properties perhaps seems slightly better (nanograin size at the lower limit, and hardness and toughness at the higher limit), but principally because the aqueous colloidal processing of these nanocomposites is much simpler [18].

4. Conclusions

We have described a parametric study to optimize the conditions for the liquid-phase assisted SPS of both SiC nanoceramics and SiC/CNT nanocomposites, using to that end different

powder mixtures all prepared by aqueous colloidal processing. Based on the results and analyses, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. It is possible to fabricate SiC nanoceramics and SiC/CNT nanocomposites by liquid-phase assisted SPS. Thus, by judicious control of the SPS conditions, and particularly of the SPS temperature, the nanostructure of the starting nanopowders can be retained during the densification heat-treatment, without CNT degradation in the case of the nanocomposites.
2. The degree of densification increases with increasing SPS temperature, with dense nanoceramics and nanocomposites being obtained at and above 1700 °C. Nanograin size also increases with increasing SPS temperature. CNTs located at grain boundaries inhibit, however, nanograin growth somewhat.
3. As the SPS temperature increases up to 1700 °C, the CNT crystallinity gradually increases, and above this temperature the CNTs begin to degrade.
4. Hardness of these nanoceramics and nanocomposites increases with increasing SPS temperature up to 1700 °C. Above this temperature, the hardness of the nanoceramics remains unchanged, while the nanocomposites soften. These trends are explicable in terms of the degrees of densification achieved and the CNT degradation above 1700 °C. Under the same SPS conditions, the nanoceramics are harder than the nanocomposites, as is attributable to the greater hardness of the SiC nanograins.
5. Fracture toughness varies relatively little with the SPS temperature. More noticeably, under the same SPS conditions, nanocomposites are, according to the Vickers indentation tests, tougher than the corresponding nanoceramics.

6. Considering the combination of degrees of densification, nanograin sizes, values of hardness and fracture toughness, and CNT crystallinity, 1700 °C is proposed as being the optimal SPS temperature (as measured by the radial optical pyrometer) for the fabrication of these nanoceramics and nanocomposites. A few minutes of soaking at 1700 °C are a required condition, while pressure (above 60 MPa) does not seem to be a critical SPS variable.
7. The morphology and surface functionalization of the CNTs do not condition the densification of the nanocomposites if the dispersion of the different phases is adequate. Also, regardless of the exact type of CNTs introduced, the nanocomposites all have similar nanograin sizes and values of hardness and fracture toughness. Nonetheless, fine-CNTs seem to be the most advisable choice for the fabrication of these nanocomposites.

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Figure Captions

Figure 1. SPS-densification curves as functions of target temperature (in the range 1600–1800 °C) for the mixtures of (A) nano-SiC+nano-YAG and (B) nano-SiC+nano-YAG+ref-CNTs. Other SPS conditions used are 75 MPa pressure and 5-min soaking time.

Figure 2. Evolution of the vacuum level during a typical SPS tests for the nano-SiC+nano-YAG powder mixture.

Figure 3. SPS-densification curve as a function of time for the mixture of nano-SiC+nano-YAG with a target temperature of 1600 °C. Other SPS conditions used are 75 MPa pressure and 5-min soaking time. The dashed line marks the end of the non-isothermal heating regime and the onset of the isothermal heating regime at 1600 °C.

Figure 4. FE-SEM micrographs of the polished surface for the SiC nanocomposite with ref-CNTs resulting from SPS cycles interrupted at temperatures (A) below the densification jump, at 1094 °C, and (B) above the densification jump, at 1255 °C. The SPS pressure used is 75 MPa.

Figure 5. FE-SEM micrographs of the fracture surface for the SiC nanoceramics resulting from SPS cycles with target temperatures of (A) 1600 °C, (B) 1700 °C, and (C) 1800 °C. Other SPS conditions used are 75 MPa pressure and 5-min soaking time.

Figure 6. FE-SEM micrographs of the fracture surface for the SiC nanocomposites with ref-CNTs resulting from SPS cycles with target temperatures of (A) 1600 °C, (B) 1700 °C, and (C) 1800 °C. Other SPS conditions used are 75 MPa pressure and 5-min soaking time. The insets are micrographs at higher magnification to show the presence of CNTs.

Figure 7. XRD pattern of the SiC nanoceramics resulting from the SPS cycle with target temperature of 1700 °C, pressure of 75 MPa and soaking time of 5 min.

Figure 8. Raman spectra of the as-received ref-CNTs and of the SiC nanocomposites with ref-CNTs resulting from the SPS cycles with target temperatures in the range 1600–1800 °C. Other SPS conditions used are 75 MPa pressure and 5-min soaking time. The peak indexing is indicated.

Figure 9. FE-SEM micrographs of the fracture surface for the SiC nanocomposites with CNTs labelled as (A) thin, (B) thick, (C) long, (D) nsg, (E) acid, and (F) graph, in all cases resulting from SPS cycles with target temperature of 1700 °C, pressure of 75, and soaking time of 5 min. The insets are micrographs at higher magnification to show the presence of CNTs.

Table captions

Table I. Degree of densification of the nanoceramics and nanocomposites with ref-CNTs depending on the SPS conditions used.

Type	SPS conditions			Density (%; ± 0.6)
	Temperature (°C)	Pressure (MPa)	Time (min)	
nanoceramic	1600	75	5	89.9
		75	0	87.0
	1650	75	3	97.0
		75	5	97.5
	1700	75	5	100
		100	5	100
	1750	75	5	100
	1800	60	0	98
		75	3	100
	75	5	100	
nanocomposite	1600	75	5	88.9
		75	0	86.2
	1650	75	3	95.4
		75	5	96.1
	1700	75	5	100
		100	5	100
	1750	75	5	100
	1800	60	0	98
		75	3	100
	75	5	100	

Table II. Microstructural and mechanical properties of the nanoceramics and nanocomposites with ref-CNTs depending on the target SPS temperature used (75 MPa pressure and 5-min soaking time).

Type	SPS temperature (°C)	Grain size (nm)	Hardness (GPa)	Fracture toughness (MPa·m ^{1/2})
nanoceramic	1600	56±23	15.1±0.8	2.9±0.4
	1650	73±25	19.8±0.9	2.8±0.4
	1700	87±26	21.7±0.7	2.3±0.3
	1750	121±30	21.3±0.8	2.4±0.2
	1800	157±52	21.4±0.9	2.4±0.3
nanocomposite	1600	55±27	10±1	3.3±0.6
	1650	59±21	15.5±0.9	3.3±0.5
	1700	65±28	19.9±0.6	3.2±0.3
	1750	94±28	18.6±0.7	3.2±0.2
	1800	131±29	18.3±0.8	3.2±0.2

Table III. Band analysis of the Raman spectra registered for as-received ref-CNTs and for the nanocomposites with ref-CNTs fabricated by SPS at different temperatures (75 MPa pressure and 5-min soaking time).

Type	SPS temperature (°C)	Intensity ratios	
		I _D /I _G	I _{2D} /I _D
as-received CNTs	—	2.11	0.23
nanocomposite with ref-CNTs	1600	1.72	0.39
	1650	1.66	0.40
	1700	0.47	0.88
	1750	1.27	0.65
	1800	1.34	0.57

Table IV. Microstructural and mechanical properties of the nanocomposites fabricated by SPS at 1700 °C (75 MPa pressure and 5-min soaking time) using different types of CNTs as reinforcements.

CNT type (<i>L</i>, <i>T</i>, <i>SF</i>)	Density (%; ±0.6)	Grain size (nm)	Hardness (GPa)	Fracture toughness (MPa·m^{1/2})
thin (0.5–2, 8–15, OH ⁻)	100	64±23	19.8±0.5	3.2±0.2
ref (0.5–2, 10–20, OH ⁻)	100	65±28	19.9±0.6	3.2±0.3
thick (0.5–2, 50–80, OH ⁻)	99.7	71±30	19.8±0.7	2.9±0.3
long (10–30, 10–20, OH ⁻)	99.2	75±24	19.9±0.9	3.0±0.2
nsg (0.5–2, 10–20, none)	98.9	75±28	19.4±1.1	2.9±0.4
acid (0.5–2, 10–20, COOH ⁻)	100	70±32	19.4±0.9	2.8±0.3
graph (10–30, 10–20, graphitized)	99.3	66±38	19.9±0.9	2.8±0.2

L denotes the length in μm, *T* the thickness in nm, and *SF* the surface functionalization of the CNTs.

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Figure 7

